

REPORT:

*A2.2.3 Documented example of the
test protocol for hydrodynamic
resistance, flow rate and volume*

Work package 2

This report was written as part of activity A2.2.3 from the EMPIR Establishing Metrology Standards in Microfluidic Devices (MFMET) project. The three-year European project commenced on 1st June 2021 and focused on providing a generic methodology of accurate measurement of a particular quantity in a microfluidic device by utilising standardised methods and reference documents, e.g. VIM & GUM. This report was updated in April 2024. For more details about this project, please visit www.mfmet.eu

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1. Scope

This document describes the documented example performed at CETIAT and IPQ to demonstrate the application of flow-related test protocols developed under task A2.2.

Activity number	Activity description	Partners (Lead in bold)
A2.2.3 M18	Using the test protocols produced in A2.2.2, CETIAT, DTI and IPQ with support from CMI, TUBITAK, INESC MN, and HSG-IMIT will perform a documented example (i.e. the documented example will apply the test protocol to a specific example, such as a flow rate calibration). The documented example will be performed in laboratories of IPQ, CIETIAT and DTI.	CETIAT , INESC MN, DTI, IPQ, CMI, TUBITAK, HSG-IMIT

2. Introduction

To illustrate the flow-related test protocols described in the report of activity 2.2.2 [1], CETIAT performed a hydrodynamic resistance test of a polymer microfluidic chip (described in section 3). The tests performed include:

- Flow rate measurement, using mass flowmeters
- Pressure drop measurements
- Hydrodynamic resistance calculation.

IPQ performed the measurements of:

- Flow rate measurement using the gravimetric and front track methods
- Volume using the gravimetric method.

The following paragraphs describe the device under test, the test setup, the realisation, and the results of the different tests performed.

This report makes use of the definition of *hydrodynamic resistance* as stated in [1], [2] and the ISO 10991:2023 (term [3.2.8](#)). It is also frequently called *flow resistivity*, even though referencing to the extensive property. It describes the relationship between a volumetric flow in a fluid conduit and the pressure difference that is necessary for driving it. The Hagen-Poiseuille equation describes such a relationship for a steady-state, laminar flow of incompressible, Newtonian fluid in a long cylindrical [3]. Hydrodynamic resistance is defined as the ratio of the pressure difference and the volumetric flow:

$$\Delta P = Q \times R_H$$

With:

- ΔP the pressure difference
- Q the volumetric flow
- R_H the hydrodynamic resistance.

3. Device under test

The device under test at CETIAT was a "Fluidic 157" microfluidic chip provided by Microfluidic ChipShop (see [4]) with the following characteristics:

- The microfluidic device material is entirely comprised of TOPAS, which is a COC – cyclic olefin copolymer – resin.
- The chip contains 8 identical, parallel channels of 100 μm width, 100 μm depth, and 18 mm length.
- The chip consists of a 75.5 mm by 25.5 mm microscope slide.
- The chip has Luer fluidic interfaces (ports), similar to "female mini Luer port" integrated directly on the chip. Those ports can be found as "stand alone" ports (see for example [5])

Figure 1 shows a schematic of the device under test.

Figure 1: Schematic of the device under test.

Figure 2 shows the device under test mounted on the test bench used for hydrodynamic resistance tests.

Figure 2: Device under test during hydrodynamic resistance testing.

IPQ performed the volume and flow measurements on 3 different chips, shown on Figure 3. Two are made of TOPAS (a polymer for medical use) provided by Microfluidic ChipShop and one of PDMS manufactured by INESC MN:

Id	Description	Material	Dimensions (mm)
a	1 channel with two 0.9 mm inlet holes, manufactured by INESC MN	PDMS	40 x 10
b	16 parallel channels with fluid interface holes, model 10000198, batch Z1112070	TOPAS	75.5 x 25.5 x 1.5
c	16 parallel channels with mini Luer fluidic interface, model 10000168, batch JI125176	TOPAS	75.5 x 25.5 x 4

Figure 3: chips used by IPQ for volume and flow tests

4. Test setup

4.1. Hydrodynamic resistance determined at CETIAT

Figure 4 presents the principle of the test setup used for the hydrodynamic resistance test. Figure 5 shows the actual setup at CETIAT.

Figure 4: Schematic of the hydrodynamic resistance test setup.
 (F) flow sensor, (P) pressure sensor, (O) outlet of the microfluidic chip under test.

Figure 5: CETIAT's test setup for hydrodynamic resistance measurement.

The hydrodynamic resistance test setup used the following equipment:

- Pressure controller:
 - Elveflow OB1 MkII (the 0-200 mbar channel was pre-calibrated by comparison to an ISO 17025 calibrated pressure sensor and used to control and measure the pressure readings).
- Flow sensors (pre-calibrated at CETIAT by comparison to the French primary standard for liquid flow, also ISO 17025 accredited):
 - Bronkhorst ML120 (83 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$ full range, readings acquired using the FlowPlot software)
 - Elveflow MFS 2 (7 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$ full range, reading acquired using the ESI software)
- Thermo-hygro-barometer (pre-calibrated at CETIAT by comparison to the French primary standard for hygrometry, also ISO 17025 accredited):
 - ROTRONIC LOG-HC2-P1 / HC2-C05 for measuring temperature, humidity, and ambient pressure of the environment in which the device was tested.

All instruments were calibrated over their full operating ranges. The fluid used for the tests was ultra-pure degassed water:

- conductivity inferior to 0.06 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$
- filtered at 0.2 μm
- density of 998.2 kg/m^3 at 20 $^{\circ}\text{C}$
- viscosity of 1.002 $\text{mPa}\cdot\text{s}$.

From the pressure controller to the device under test, all tubing used to connect the components of the setup was 316L stainless steel with an outer diameter of 1/16" for a total length of 30 cm.

At the inlet port of the device under test, a Luer male to threaded Upchurch Scientific adapter, with an additional threaded female-female Upchurch Scientific elbow, was used to connect the fluidic path to the device under test, as shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6: Adapter used to connect the fluidic setup to the device under test.

Below are the references of three assembly components from the device under test to the 1/16" stainless steel pipe:

- P-683-01: Luer male to threaded Upchurch adapter
- P-430: Threaded female-female Upchurch 1/16" OD PEEK elbow
- P-235: Upchurch Flangeless Nut for 1/16" OD

4.2. Flow rate determined outside the chip at IPQ

Figure 7 presents the test setup used for the flow test at IPQ using the gravimetric method.

Figure 7: Gravimetric flow setup.

The flow is generated by a programmable syringe pump with flow measurement range from 2 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$ to 500 mL/min ($\pm 0.35\%$, 0.1% reproducibility, Nexus 3000 infuse/withdraw system, Chemix Precision Syringe Pumps). PE tube of 1.26 mm inner diameter was used in the flow path.

Figure 8 presents the test setup used for the flow test at IPQ using the front track method.

Figure 8: Front track flow setup.

A high-resolution Alvium 1800 U-1240 camera of 12 Mpx of resolution with Qioptic Optem 7:1 telecentric zoom lens was used. The camera is connected to a computer and uses an image processing script in Python programming language that identifies the meniscus and calculates its position. The flow is generated by a programmable syringe pump with flow measurement range from 2 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$ to 500 mL/min ($\pm < 0.35\%$, 0.1 % reproducibility, Nexus 3000 infuse/withdraw system, Chemix Precision Syringe Pumps. PE tube of 1.26 mm inner diameter was used.

4.3. Volume determined at IPQ

The volume of the 3 chips was determined using the gravimetric method, a XP205 Mettler balance with 0.01 mg resolution was used. The reference liquid is ultrapure water. The liquid temperature was measure with a PT100 sensor of 0.01 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ resolution.

5. Test procedure

5.1. Hydrodynamic resistance

The setup, test equipment recommendations, and test procedure detailed in MFMET report A2.2.2 (section 2) has been followed to experimentally assess the hydrodynamic resistance of one of the channels of the device under test. The following steps outlines this procedure:

- a. Measure the flow and pressure of the full setup (pressure controller, flow meter, and device under test) for 5 different inlet pressures.
- b. Measure the flow and pressure of the setup without the device under test for the same 5 different inlet pressures (pressure controller and flow meter).
- c. Calculate the hydrodynamic resistance of:
 - c.1. The full setup
 - c.2. The setup without the device under test
 - c.3. The device under test alone (by subtracting the hydrodynamic resistance of the setup without device under test to the one the full setup).

5.2. Flow

The following methodology has been followed to experimentally assess the flow of one of the device under test's channels.

In the gravimetric method, the syringe or flow generator is filled with high ultrapure water from a reservoir through an automatic switch valve. A high flow rate is imposed to the system by

automatically actuating the switch valve hence purging the flow line from air bubbles which can significantly affect flow stability and introduce flow errors. This procedure is repeated until the flow circuit is completely purged (10 minutes of continuous water flow is usually sufficient). Additionally, the syringe is connected to the channel to be tested at the chip, and the tube ending is immersed in the weighing vessel to prevent flow oscillations due to droplet detachment.

The front tracking method consists of following the position of the meniscus of a liquid (liquid/air interface) inside a capillary tube over time. Knowing the displacement of the meniscus over time and the internal cross-section area of the capillary it is possible to calculate the flow rate. A 1.6-mm inner diameter plastic capillary was connected to a specific channel of the chip. The flow was generated by syringe Nexus pump that was connected to the chip.

5.3. Volume

The volume determination by gravimetric method consists of weighing the chip under calibration when empty and again when full of an appropriate liquid. Each channel is tested separately. The difference obtained in the weighing measurements gives the mass of contained liquid in a specific channel. The tests using the gravimetric method for volume determination were performed in the following conditions:

- a. Acclimatization time of 24 h, all the instruments and the water stood in the same room for 24 hours
- b. Controlled room temperature equal to $(20 \pm 3) ^\circ\text{C}$
- c. Room temperature variation during the measurements not more than $1 ^\circ\text{C}$
- d. Humidity room above 50 %
- e. Weigh the empty and dry microchip
- f. Measure the water temperature
- g. Fill the microchip with water, ensuring no bubbles are inside
- h. Weigh the chip full of water

During the tests, the temperature of the water and the air, the relative humidity and the atmospheric pressure need to be continually measured and recorded.

6. Experimental results

6.1. Hydrodynamic resistance

Table 1 below shows the experimental hydrodynamic resistance results obtained for the measurement of the full setup from the pressure sensor to the device under test outlet. Flow and pressure measurements were acquired synchronously at a 50 Hz sampling frequency for 180 seconds for each plateau at decreasing and increasing pressure and flow steps to include hysteresis effect in the overall hydrodynamic resistance evaluation.

The average expanded relative uncertainty on the differential pressure measurement is 0.55 % ($k=2$). The coverage factor k indicates approximately 95 % confidence when it equals 2. The average expanded relative uncertainty on the flow rate measurement is 2.31 % ($k=2$). All average measurements of pressure and flow were repeated two times. The measurement uncertainties have been evaluated according to GUM using the law of propagation of uncertainty, including calibration, reading, and repeatability uncertainty sources.

In this case, the differential pressure is calculated as the measured pressure (at the pressure sensor location) minus the measured atmospheric pressure. The pressure was zeroed prior to testing to account for any discrepancies associated with the hydrostatic pressure head.

The associated hydrodynamic resistance is calculated as the ratio of the mean pressure step value (difference between two consecutive values of differential pressure) over the corresponding mean flow rate step value (difference between two consecutive values of flow rate) for each step. The resulting resistivity is then obtained by averaging over the steps. Following this procedure, possible constant offsets in differential pressure and flow rate are cancelled.

The relative expanded uncertainty on the hydrodynamic resistance is calculated as the square root of the quadratic sum of the pressure and flow measurement uncertainties. The final uncertainty of the averaged value of hydrodynamic resistance also contains the corresponding standard deviation of the averaged data (repeatability).

Table 1: Experimental results with chip.

Measurements				Calculation result
Differential pressure 1	Volume flow rate 1	Differential pressure 2	Volume flow rate 2	Hydrodynamic resistance
[kPa]	[$\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$]	[kPa]	[$\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$]	[$10^{12} \text{ Pa}\cdot\text{s}/\text{m}^3$]
3.90	18.0	3.20	14.0	10.5
3.20	14.0	2.50	9.0	8.40
2.50	9.0	2.05	6.0	9.00
2.05	6.0	1.50	2.5	9.43
Average				9.33
U(k=2)				1.79

Figure 9 shows the pressure and flow readings during the test of the full setup.

Figure 9: Pressure (blue) and flow (red) readings during the hydrodynamic resistance test with chip.

To assess the hydrodynamic resistance of the measurement setup by itself and act as a control, the microfluidic chip was removed from the circuit as schematized in the Figure 10. Note that the outlet of the stainless-steel pipe at the outlet of the flowmeter is still equipped with the same fittings and kept at the same height as for the measurement of the chip, to avoid discrepancies between the test setup with and without microfluidic chip.

Figure 10: Schematic of the hydrodynamic resistance test setup without chip. (F) flow sensor, (P) pressure sensor, (O) outlet of the test setup.

Table 2 shows the experimental results of hydrodynamic resistance measured for the setup without chip (see Figure 10). The uncertainties on pressure and flow rate measurements are similar to the one obtained for the setup with chip.

Table 2: Experimental results without chip.

Measurements				Calculation result
Differential pressure 1 [kPa]	Volume flow rate 1 [$\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$]	Differential pressure 2 [kPa]	Volume flow rate 2 [$\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$]	Hydrodynamic resistance [$10^{12} \text{ Pa}\cdot\text{s}/\text{m}^3$]
3.90	57.0	3.20	48.0	4.67
3.20	48.0	2.50	37.5	4.00
2.50	37.5	2.05	28.0	2.84
2.05	28.0	1.50	18.0	3.30
Average				3.70
U(k=2)				1.61

Figure 11 shows the pressure and flow readings during the test without the chip. Notice that while Figure 11 has many measurement pairs of pressure and flow, Table 2 only presents measurement pairs where the pressure matches the pressures from Table 1.

Figure 11: Pressure (blue) and flow (red) readings during the hydrodynamic resistance test without chip.

To calculate the hydrodynamic resistance of the device under test by itself, the hydrodynamic resistance obtained for the control setup without the microfluidic chip is subtracted from the hydrodynamic resistance of the entire circuit with the microfluidic chip.

An average experimental value of $5.63 \cdot 10^{12} \text{ Pa}\cdot\text{s}/\text{m}^3$ is obtained for the device under test across all the specified test conditions, with an overall associated expanded relative uncertainty of 42.8 %

(k=2). Table 3 sums up the hydrodynamic resistance values for the circuit with chip, the circuit without chip, and the chip itself, along with their associated expanded uncertainties.

Table 3: Device under test hydrodynamic resistance calculation.

Setup	Hydrodynamic resistance [10 ¹² Pa·s/m ³]	Uncertainty [10 ¹² Pa·s/m ³]
Circuit with chip	9.33	1.79
Circuit without chip	3.70	1.61
Chip itself	5.63	2.41

6.2. Flow rate

Table 4 shows the experimental results obtained for the measurements of flow rate using the gravimetric method for Chip A, Chip C and PDMS chip.

Table 4: Gravimetric flow measurements.

Chip	Nominal Flow [mL/h]	Measured Flow [mL/h]	Error [%]	U [%]
PDMS	0.001	0.00092	8	23
	0.1	0.0993	0.7	4.6
	0.1	0.0993	0.7	2.5
	1	0.9945	0.55	2.4
A	0.01	0.0099	1.0	5.0
	0.1	0.0983	1.7	3.8
	1	0.9907	0.93	0.19
C	0.01	0.0069	31	5
	0.1	0.097	2.6	3.4
	1	1.017	-1.7	3.0

Table 5 shows the experimental results obtained for the measurements of flow rate using the front track method for Chip A, Chip C and PDMS chip.

Table 5: Front track flow measurements.

Chip	Nominal Flow [mL/h]	Measured Flow [mL/h]	Error [%]	U (%)
INESC MN	0.001	-0.0014	-170.8	14.0
	0.01	0.0113	-11.8	3.3
	0.1	0.0961	4.0	2.6
	1	1.0257	-2.5	4.0
A	0.01	0.0095	5.3	3.7
	0.1	0.0967	3.4	2.8
	1	0.9819	1.8	6.2
C	0.01	-0.0033	-402.8	43.3
	0.1	0.0996	0.5	1.9
	1	1.0259	-2.5	4.0

The results of both method for the same channel were compared using the normalized error E_n are presented in Table 6. Most of the results obtained are consistent, with $|E_n| \leq 1$.

Table 6: Determination of the normalized error.

Chip	Nominal Flow [mL/h]	E_n
PDMS	0.001	-6.63
	0.01	-2.21
	0.1	0.92
	1	0.66
A	0.01	-0.69
	0.1	-0.36
	1	-0.15
C	0.01	9.94
	0.1	0.55
	1	0.17

6.3. Volume

Table 7 shows the experimental results obtained for the measurements of volume rate using the gravimetric method for Chip A, Chip C and PDMS chip.

Table 7: Volume determination.

GRAVIMETRIC METHOD			
Chip	Channel	Volume [mL]	U [mL]
PDMS	1	0.00277	0.00004
A	1	0.00390	0.00010
	8	0.00426	0.00014
C	1	0.00387	0.00016
	13	0.00385	0.00007

The channels in the TOPAS chips have similar volumes.

7. Dry test: theoretical calculation of hydrodynamic resistance

Hydrodynamic resistance can also be calculated theoretically, using the following equation for square section microchannels [2]:

$$R_{H,sq} = \frac{12 \mu L}{1 - 0,917 \times 0,63} \left(\frac{1}{h^4} \right) \quad (1)$$

With:

- μ the dynamic viscosity
- L the length of the channel
- h the height of the channel, which equals the width for square cross section microchannel.

It is additionally assumed that the Reynolds number is small (< 10); that only a small fluid mass per distance unit is used, so gravity can be considered negligible; and that all other sources of resistance besides the $100 \mu\text{m} \times 100 \mu\text{m}$ cross section of the channel contribute negligibly to the overall hydrodynamic resistance in the microfluidic system.

Equation (1) yields a hydrodynamic resistance of $4.97 \cdot 10^{12} \text{ Pa}\cdot\text{s}/\text{m}^3$ for the following values:

- $\mu = 0.001 \text{ Pa}\cdot\text{s}$ (water at $20 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$)

- $L = 0.0175$ m. The length from the axis of one connector cup to the axis of another connector cup is 18 mm, but the bottom part of the connector cup has a diameter of 0.5 mm. Therefore, the actual length of the straight channel itself is 17.5 mm
- $h = 0.0001$ m (100 μm x 100 μm square section micro-channel)

Bruus presents another equation for calculating the hydrodynamic resistance theoretically [3]:

$$R_H = \frac{\Delta P}{Q} = \frac{12 \mu L}{h^4} \frac{1}{1 - \sum_{n, \text{odd}}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^5} \frac{192}{\pi^5} \tanh\left(n \frac{\pi}{2}\right)} \quad (2)$$

The original equation has been modified by substituting the conduit width w with the conduit height h , so it describes a square profile conduit, with the same variable names as in equation (1)

Equation (2) was derived by solving the Navier-Stokes equation with no slip boundary condition at the conduit walls, and by using an expansion with a Fourier series. It contains an infinite series, where the terms have a factor decreasing as $1/n^5$ for increasing odd integers n . Bruus states this relation results in an error of 13 % in the worst case, where $h = w$.

Note that equation (1) can be derived from equation (2) using the following approximations:

- The sum is limited to $n = 1$.
- $192/\pi^5 \approx 0.63$
- $\tanh(\pi/2) \approx 0.917$

With the same values for μ , L and h , equation (2) yields a hydrodynamic resistance of $4.98 \cdot 10^{12}$ Pa·s/m³. The result from equation (1) was indeed a good approximation, as the relative difference between both calculated hydrodynamic resistances is about -0.14 %.

8. Dry test: CFD calculation of hydrodynamic resistance

In this section are described the computational fluid dynamics (CFD) simulations of flow in the microfluidic chip using COMSOL Multiphysics and OpenFOAM softwares, as well as the hydrodynamic resistance results based on these CFD models.

8.1. Geometry of the microfluidic channel including connector parts

The simulated microchannel has a square cross section with dimensions 100 μm x 100 μm . The channel is equipped with a connector part at both ends. A detail of this part can be seen in Figure 12. The simulated geometry consists of the microchannel (c) together with the “connector cup” (b) at both ends (see Figure 13). The length of the setup from one axis of the connector cup to the other is 18 mm (see Figure 13). Since the distance of the connector cup axis from the microchannel inlet is 0.25 mm, the length of the micro-channel itself is 17.5 mm. Drawing of the connector cup is shown in Figure 14.

Figure 12: Detail of the connector part of the microchannel:
 (a) cylinder where a plug of a supply tube is inserted (not part of the CFD simulation),
 (b) volume ("connector cup") connecting the pipe outlet with the inlet of the microchannel (part of the CFD simulation),
 (c) the microchannel. The analogous description holds also for the connector part at the opposite side of the micro-channel.

Figure 13: Geometry of the microchannel with the connector cups used for the simulation.

Figure 14: Geometry of the connector cups (dimensions in μm).

8.2. CFD simulations

To check for the influence of the CFD setup on the result, the hydrodynamic resistance was simulated using two different softwares: Comsol Multiphysics V5.1 and OpenFOAM.

The simulation is based on the Navier-Stokes equations considering Newtonian, incompressible fluid and assuming laminar and stationary flow. Properties of the fluid (water, Newtonian fluid) were set at 20 °C. Table 8 describes the parameters of the two CFD setups.

Table 8: Comparison of the two CFD setups.

Software	COMSOL	OpenFOAM
Solver	The Microfluidics module with physics-controlled mesh was used to solve the flow velocity and pressure field	The simpleFoam solver was used and a hexahedral mesh with density of 40 x 40 cells in the microchannel cross section was selected based on a mesh convergence study. The complete geometry is made of 15,168,000 cells and no boundary refinement was used because the flow is laminar.
Conditions	Fixed inlet and outlet pressure boundary conditions were imposed and several simulations were performed for various inlet-outlet pressure differences ranging from 1 kPa to 5 kPa.	Constant value of flow velocity (piston profile) was prescribed at the inlet and several simulations were performed for different inlet velocities corresponding to flow rates from 15.7 μL/min to 38.9 μL/min. Zero velocity gradient condition was used at the outlet and for pressure the zero gradient was used at the inlet and the wall and a fixed value at the outlet.
	No-slip boundary condition for velocity was used at the wall.	
Output	Volumetric flow rate Q for a given differential pressure ΔP between the two ends of the geometry	Differential pressure ΔP for a given volumetric flow rate Q
	The hydrodynamic resistance is then given has: $R_H = \frac{\Delta P}{Q} \quad (3)$	

The OpenFOAM model was first tested on a geometry with the straight microchannel only (no connector cups) for which the analytical solution is known (see eq. (2)). For the length of the microchannel $L = 17.5$ mm, height (= width) of the square cross section $h = 0.1$ mm and dynamic viscosity μ of the pure water at 20 °C this formula gives a value of $4.98 \cdot 10^{12}$ Pa·s/m³. The hydrodynamic resistance calculated from the CFD simulation with the straight microchannel (no connector cups) was $R_H = 5.00 \cdot 10^{12}$ Pa·s/m³ deviating from the analytical prediction by 0.4 %.

Figure 15 presents the results of the simulations for the complete microchannel with connector cups. The hydrodynamic resistance appears slightly dependent on the flow rate.

Figure 15: Hydrodynamic resistance (hydrodynamic resistance) as a function of the flow rate in the microchannel with connector cups.

9. Results analysis and discussion

Comparison of results for hydrodynamic resistance obtained by various methods – experimental (section 6), analytical (section 7) and CFD (section 8) is given in Table 9. We see that the CFD prediction of the hydrodynamic resistance of the microchannel with connector cups is lower than the experimental result by 7.9 % in case of OpenFOAM and by 6.3 % in the case of COMSOL. The analytical prediction which considers the straight channel only (without the connector cups) is then 12 % lower than the experimental value. Therefore, taking into account the total experimental uncertainty of 42.8 %, these results are in good agreement.

Table 9: Comparison of the hydrodynamic resistance obtained with various methods.

Setup	Method	Hydrodynamic resistance [10 ¹² Pa.s/m ³]	Uncertainty [10 ¹² Pa.s/m ³]
Circuit with chip	Measured	9.33	1.79
Circuit without chip	Measured	3.70	1.61
Chip itself	Calculated from measurements	5.63	2.41
Straight channel part of the chip	Theoretical formula	4.98	
	CFD OpenFoam	5.18	
Chip (straight channel with connectors)	CFD COMSOL Multiphysics	10 mbar: 5.20	
		15 mbar: 5.24	
		20 mbar: 5.27	
		25 mbar: 5.28	
		30 mbar: 5.29	
		35 mbar: 5.30	
		40 mbar: 5.30	
		45 mbar: 5.31	
	50 mbar: 5.31		
	Average COMSOL	5.28	

The test setup shown in Figure 4, characterizes the hydrodynamic resistance from the outlet of the pressure controller to the outlet of the microfluidic chip or outlet of the test setup. Thus, the flow pathway of the system contains not only the device under investigation, but also 1/16" tubing, fittings, and the flow sensor. This report presents a step-by-step methodology for how to accurately test hydrodynamic resistance in a microfluidic chip and calculate the hydrodynamic resistance associated only with the microfluidic device under investigation. Most of the hydrodynamic resistance is associated with the microfluidic chip, which is expected considering that the 100 μm x 100 μm microchannel is the smallest flow path cross section of the system.

Despite most of the hydrodynamic resistance being associated with the microfluidic chip, the contributions to the hydrodynamic resistance from the flow sensor, tubing, and fittings are still large enough to significantly affect the total hydrodynamic resistance. Considering these findings, it is important to consider the hydrodynamic resistance associated with all the fluid-contacting components of the test system. This test protocol can be standardized to accurately determine the hydrodynamic resistance of a microfluidic devices.

10. Conclusion

This report details documented examples for the accurate measurement of hydrodynamic resistance, flow, and volume in a microfluidic chip setup. The experimental results for hydrodynamic resistance, encompassing measurements from the pressure sensor to the device under test outlet, reveal an average hydrodynamic resistance of $5.63 \cdot 10^{12} \text{ Pa}\cdot\text{s}/\text{m}^3$, subject to an overall expanded relative uncertainty of 42.8 % ($k=2$). This uncertainty analysis, conducted in accordance with the Guide to the Expression of Uncertainty in Measurement (GUM), underscores the rigor applied in assessing measurement uncertainties, including calibration, reading, and repeatability sources.

Comparison with theoretical values, indicates a 12% deviation from an analytical formula and even lower deviations from CFD computations, which falls within an acceptable range given the associated uncertainty. Furthermore, the documented example extends its analysis to include a control setup without the microfluidic chip. Despite most of the hydrodynamic resistance being attributed to the microfluidic chip, the interconnected components, such as tubing, fittings, and the flow sensor, significantly contribute to the overall hydrodynamic resistance.

The presented documented example, following a step-by-step methodology, provides a robust framework for standardizing flow, volume, and hydrodynamic resistance measurements in microfluidic devices. Notably, the study emphasizes the importance of considering the contributions of all fluid-contacting components within the test system, highlighting their substantial impact on the total hydrodynamic resistance.

In conclusion, the determined average experimental value, although associated with a rather high relative uncertainty of 42.8 % ($k=2$) for the hydrodynamic resistance example, demonstrates the viability of the proposed methodology. The observed maximum 12 % discrepancy between experimental and theoretical values of hydrodynamic resistance is deemed not significant within the context of the overall uncertainty, affirming the reliability of the study's findings. This report contributes valuable insights to the field of microfluidics, offering a robust approach to flow-related quantities characterization and encouraging further refinement in measurement techniques.

11. References

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